

Beyond Strong Social Robotics A Relational Perspective

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Abstract. This epistemological contribution offers a theoretical reframing of the strong AI debate within the field of social robotics, where the classical strong/weak AI dichotomy has evolved into a tension between two identifiable approaches: strong and weak social robotics. The former seeks to replicate human-like social competencies in artificial agents, grounded in an individualistic model of embodiment; the latter designs robots that evoke social presence without reproducing the deep affective and cognitive processes characteristic of living systems. Despite their differences, both perspectives share the assumption that social competence must be an intrinsic property of the robot.

In this article, we challenge this view. Our core proposal is a relational and embodied epistemological framework that conceives sociality not as rooted in the internal (whether “natural” or “artificial”) physiology of individual agents, but as emerging from dynamic processes of human–robot coordination.

This theoretical reconceptualization, we argue, also calls for a shift in the ethical domain, which we articulate through *synthetic ethics*: a context-sensitive, practice-based ethical approach. Moving beyond merely negative ethical framings of social robots, synthetic ethics treats human–robot interaction as a site of ongoing experimentation, where ethical and relational significance are co-constructed. We suggest that this framework enables ethics to engage with the novelty introduced by emerging social machines, and may orient their diffusion in ways that foster human self-understanding, social development, and sustained moral growth.

Keywords: Strong vs weak social robotics, Social and affective coordination, Synthetic ethics.

1 Introduction

Recent debates on AI have long centered on whether machines can truly “understand” or “only simulate” human cognition. In the field of social robotics, this tension has assumed a new configuration. Traditional AI’s *strong versus weak dichotomy* finds a parallel in what we now refer to as “strong” versus “weak” social robotics. According to this emerging distinction, *strong social robotics* seeks to transfer the social capacities of human individuals to robotic agents by reproducing, based on artificial mechanisms, the structures that ground human sociality—understood here through an individualistic model of social embodiment. In contrast, *weak social robotics* is concerned with crafting machines that evoke social presence through cues such as anthropomorphic design and programmed behavioral responses, without delving into the deep affective and cognitive processes that characterize living systems (Damiano & Dumouchel, 2020; 2024).

In this article, we critically revisit this opposition from a relational perspective. Our aim is to question the fundamental assumption that genuine human-robot social interaction is only possible if robots replicate the neurophysiological basis of human sociality (as in strong social robotics), or that interaction is inherently deceptive when such replication is absent (as in weak social robotics). This perspective holds that social robots can only be considered legitimate social actors if they reflect our individual biological substrate. If they don't, they tend to be classified merely as simulators. In this way, the question of human-robot sociality is reduced to a simplistic either/or: real when neurologically grounded as in human individuals, otherwise false. In the following pages, we challenge this dichotomy by proposing a third path, beyond the opposition between strong and weak social robotics. We suggest that in human-robot interaction, genuine social engagement, as it happens in human-human interaction, emerges from dynamic *social coordination*, understood as a process of signaling, mutual responsiveness, and adjustment between agents through which they come to coordinate their dispositions to act. This view, which builds on previous work on affective coordination and the relational nature of social interaction in human-robot contexts (Dumouchel & Damiano, 2017; Damiano & Dumouchel, 2020, 2024), reframes social competence not as an intrinsic property of the robot, but as something that unfolds within human-robot interaction itself.

As we will argue, this relational understanding opens the door to innovative, trans-disciplinary and context-sensitive ethical approaches to social robotics. Rather than rejecting social robots on abstract normative grounds—whether for being too human-like or not human-like enough—this perspective invites us to evaluate, case by case and project by project, the specific advantages and risks of human-robot social coordination. In doing so, it challenges dominant negative ethical frameworks and supports the development of experimental ethical approaches for assessing and improving the actual ethical impact of artificial agents within our social ecologies.

The primary aim of this article is to offer a reframing of social robotics grounded in a relational epistemology of sociality and affectivity. From this epistemological shift, we articulate an ethical approach—synthetic ethics—designed to guide the integration of social robots into human ecologies. The epistemological and ethical strands are thus intertwined, with the ethical implications emerging from the reconceptualization of social competence.

This paper is organized into seven short sections. After this introduction, we present our research rationale and guiding research questions (§2). We then delineate the theoretical background that underpins the strong/weak social robotics distinction (§3), discuss the role of embodiment in social robotics and introduce the relational perspective that redefines sociality as an emergent property (§4). We then analyze social and affective coordination as the driving force behind human-robot interaction (§5). Finally, we propose the concept of synthetic ethics as a guiding framework for the ethical integration of social robots into our social ecologies (§6), and we recapitulate our position (§7).

2 Framing the Argument: Research Rationale and Questions

This article offers a theoretically grounded contribution to the transdisciplinary field of social robotics, aimed at revisiting and reframing some of its foundational assumptions. Developed in active dialogue with researchers and practitioners in social robotics, this epistemological work is intended to support the co-evolution of theoretical reflection and experimental practice. Drawing on an embodied and relational approach to cognition and social interaction, we develop an epistemological exploration that complements empirical research and remains responsive to ongoing design and implementation efforts in the field.

- What assumptions underlie the dichotomy between strong and weak approaches to social robotics?
- To what extent do these assumptions rely on an individualistic notion of social competence?
- Can (human and robotic) sociality be understood as an emergent property of relational processes, rather than an intrinsic attribute of autonomous agents?
- What kind of ethical framework can express this relational shift in perspective?

These questions, while theoretical in nature, are far from abstract. We believe they are critical for understanding and orienting the transformations already underway in our social world. As recently observed by Yann LeCun at the 2025 World Economic Forum, the convergence of generative AI and robotics is expected to drive the next major wave of artificial agent development. In this anticipated "era of robotics", clarifying the foundations of human–robot sociality is a matter of increasing practical urgency. It will help shape how artificial social agents are designed, deployed, and integrated into human social ecologies—ultimately influencing how our societies evolve in response to their presence. Engaging with these questions—which underpin the analysis developed in the following sections—is not only theoretically necessary, but also practically urgent, as we collectively navigate the evolving landscape of human–robot coexistence.

3 Theoretical Background: Strong vs. Weak Social Robotics

The debate on artificial intelligence has historically hinged on the dichotomy between *strong* and *weak* AI, originally formulated by John Searle (1980, 1992). This distinction—now canonical—separates attempts to create systems that genuinely reproduce human mental work (*strong AI*) from those that merely simulate human cognition (*weak AI*). According to Searle, weak AI systems may behave as if they understand, but lack any intrinsic intentionality or semantic content; they operate purely on syntactic manipulation of symbols. This critique revealed what Searle termed the “problem of meaning”: the incapacity of computational systems to instan-

tiate genuine understanding due to their lack of biological embodiment and self-production.

In the field of social robotics, this dichotomy has been reformulated with a focus on sociability and embodiment (Damiano & Dumouchel, 2020, 2024). As previously mentioned, “strong social robotics” refers to the attempt to endow robots with *genuine* human-like social capacities, typically driven by the ambition to replicate—at least in part—the neurophysiological and embodied foundations of human sociality. These robots are expected not only to mimic social behaviors but to internalize affective and cognitive mechanisms modeled on human systems. By contrast, “weak social robotics” forgoes this aspiration. It focuses on engineering robots that elicit social responses through anthropomorphic cues and interactional scripts, without targeting the reproduction of the embodied cognitive processes that underlie human sociability.

Crucially, as we have argued elsewhere, both approaches share a fundamental assumption: that social competence is an *individual property*—something a robot either possesses or lacks, depending on how closely it mirrors human embodiment. In this light, “strong” and “weak” social robotics both presuppose an individualistic and substantialist conception of social interaction. Consequently, the tension between strong and weak approaches to social robotics, and related debates, parallel the same divide at the heart of Searle’s original distinction: either robots are truly social because they replicate human-like embodiment (and thus cross the threshold of intentionality), or they are mere simulators—social in appearance but not in substance.

In this article, we propose to move beyond this dichotomy. Rather than asking whether social robots possess the requisite internal properties to count as “truly social,” we explore an alternative approach grounded in relational embodiment and social coordination. From this perspective, social competence is not an intrinsic feature of the robot, but an emergent property of the interaction itself—as a distributed property of the human–robot relational system. This shift opens the door to new ethical and epistemological frameworks, and calls for a rethinking of both theoretical and design paradigms in social robotics. This perspective complements recent ethical analyses of social robotics that emphasize inclusive and context-sensitive design (e.g., Lin et al., 2017; Nørskov, 2017; Torras, 2024).

4 Embodiment and Sociality in Robotics: Reframing from a Relational Standpoint

Traditional approaches in social robotics have largely been influenced by embodied AI, which emphasizes the importance of a physical body in cognitive processes (e.g., Pfeifer & Scheier, 2001; Steels & Brooks, 2018). However, contemporary social robots, such as humanoid agents developed through anthropomorphic design and computational cognitive architectures, are far from achieving the autopoietic, organismal embodiment that characterizes human beings (e.g., Sandini et al., 2024). This shortfall is at the heart of the strong social robotics approach: the ambition to recreate human-like social competencies in machines.

A critical review of contemporary embodied AI reveals that many robots are designed with only superficial physical cues intended to trigger anthropomorphic projections in human users. Their physical presence, facial expressions, and programmed

gestures serve as tools to simulate social interaction. Yet, these systems do not exhibit the self-producing, self-regulating dynamics that characterize biological systems as autopoietic systems—namely, systems capable of generating and maintaining their own organization, like living cells (Maturana & Varela, 1980). This critique echoes longstanding concerns in embodied AI research about the limitations of simulative embodiment and the challenges of grounding social interaction in systems lacking organismic self-regulation (e.g., Pfeifer & Bongard, 2007; Prescott, 2012; Ziemke, 2016). However, requiring robotic agents to meet the criteria of biological autopoiesis risks overlooking alternative forms of synthetic embodiment that, while not organismic, may nonetheless be socially effective. Rather than harboring intrinsic social capabilities, they function as interfaces through which social interaction is facilitated—an approach that aligns more closely with weak social robotics. It follows that, despite their apparent differences, strong and weak social robotics converge in key respects—both in the technologies they produce and in their shared assumption that social relations depend on properties of individual agents.

From the relational standpoint we adopt, sociality is not a property of individual agents, but an emergent phenomenon arising from their interactions. This insight—arguably implicit in many current practices, especially within weak social robotics—remains largely unacknowledged in both *strong* and *weak* approaches, which, in line with an individualistic conception of sociality, continue to frame social competence as an intrinsic feature of socially “self-contained” agents. In contrast, we emphasize that in human–robot interaction—as in human–human social exchange—meaningful engagement is driven by *social coordination*: the nuanced, reciprocal exchange of communicative signals through which agents co-define their behaviors, expectations, intentions, and situated dispositions to act (Damiano & Dumouchel, 2020).

Viewed in this light, robots that lack genuine individual social capacities can contribute to dynamic social processes, provided they are embedded in contexts that support relational interaction. This reconceptualization shifts the focus of research in social robotics from the replication of human sociality to the robot’s capacity to participate in and modulate emergent social dynamics. It further suggests that the sociality of social robots lies not in what they are internally, but in what they *do* within human–robot networks.

By reframing embodiment in relational terms, our analysis challenges the assumption—central to *strong social robotics*—that effective human–robot interaction requires individually instantiated, autopoietic social capacities. At the same time, it calls for a more flexible and dynamic understanding of social competence than that typically associated with *weak social robotics*—one that is context-dependent and emerges from the interplay between human and machine.

5 Social and Affective Coordination in Human–Robot Interaction

A relational reframing of social robotics invites us to shift focus from the internal architecture of individual agents to the dynamic interplay that unfolds in interaction. In this perspective, *social coordination* emerges as the key concept for understanding how meaningful engagement between humans and robots can arise—even in the ab-

sense of biologically grounded social competencies. We use this notion to refer to the distributed processes through which agents mutually adjust their behaviors, signals, and intentions, giving rise to shared rhythms, expectations, and mutually co-defined dispositions to act. This coordination can take multiple forms—pragmatic, sensorimotor, linguistic, or affective. *Affective coordination* refers to the subtle, often unconscious alignment of emotional expressions, postures, vocal tones, and bodily cues between agents, through which reciprocal intentions and forms of social engagement are co-constructed (Dumouchel, 2019; Damiano & Dumouchel, 2024).

As we understand it, affective coordination is not a property confined to individual agents—whether animal, human, or robotic—but an emergent phenomenon distributed across interaction. This view contrasts with traditional theoretical models of social robotics, in which affective behavior is typically conceived as something the robot must internally generate. As such, this relational understanding of affective coordination sheds light on the potential for robots to engage in emotionally meaningful interactions—not by replicating emotional depth, but by shaping interactional dynamics that support relational meaning.

Understanding affective coordination as relational and distributed thus invites a re-consideration of how robots are, and may increasingly be, embedded within human affective ecologies. Affective coordination between humans and robots consists of a subtle, often unconscious alignment between human emotional experience and the affective cues engineered into robotic behavior. This dynamic process allows robots to evoke emotional responses from human partners, thereby creating a sense of social presence and engagement. While current robotic systems rely heavily on anthropomorphic design and computational algorithms to mimic human emotional expressions—and do not replicate the deep, affective-cognitive processes found in biological organisms—they can nonetheless be effective in establishing affective coordination—something they often do when their design fosters reciprocal interaction.

The main interest of this emergent, relational view of affect lies in how it calls into question the idea that genuine social interaction requires robots to possess intrinsic, human-like emotions. Indeed, what is suggested is that meaningful social dynamics can arise from the interplay between human affect and robot-evoked responses. In practice, this means that robots developed within the weak social robotics paradigm—the only kind currently effectively realized in social robotics, that is, robots that primarily imitate social cues—can participate in human–robot affective coordination, provided they are embedded within the appropriate social context. This capacity to support dynamic, co-regulated emotional engagement is what we refer to as *artificial empathy*—not as a reproduction of human–human affective coordination, but as a new, specific form of affective coordination, particular to the interactions between social robots and humans (e.g., Dumouchel & Damiano, 2017).

Such an understanding calls for a pluralistic view of affective coordination—one that recognizes the diversity of forms through which relational meaning and emotional alignment can emerge across different kinds of agents and interactional ecologies. This pluralism, in turn, invites a shift in focus: from the individual capacities of robots to the qualities of the relational contexts in which they are embedded.

By emphasizing affective coordination, our analysis foregrounds the importance of interaction dynamics over individual capacities. A shift that opens new avenues for research and design in social robotics, distinct from both strong and weak approaches,

which respectively aim to replicate internal social capacities and to simulate external social cues. By contrast, the relational approach emphasizes the emergence of social value from situated coordination, rather than from agent-bound properties. This suggests that the ethical integration of these systems may depend less on achieving “perfect human-like embodiment” and more on fostering rich, interactive environments where social meaning can emerge collectively.

6 Synthetic Ethics: Toward an Ethics in the Making

The reconceptualization of social robotics as a relational process, centered on social and affective coordination rather than intrinsic social competence, has significant ethical implications. Traditional ethical debates have primarily revolved around whether robots can genuinely “feel” emotions or possess authentic social capabilities—discussions strongly tied to the ideals of strong social robotics. However, this approach, and the criticism that underlies it, tend to lead to purely negative ethical evaluations of social robotics. On one hand, those who consider strong social robotics feasible—the creation of robots genuinely embodying human-like social competencies—emphasize the risk of robots substituting humans in essential social roles and relationships. On the other hand, those advocating weak social robotics argue that we are only capable of creating robots that evoke social presence superficially, and warn of the danger inherent in fostering illusions of genuine social relationships with machines that simulate social cues without truly possessing human-like depth of affective-cognitive processes.

However, both purely negative ethical positions—which focus narrowly on individual robots’ internal competencies or their absence—carry evident risks. By limiting themselves to a generalized condemnation of social robots, such stances offer no constructive guidance and effectively leave social robotics without the support of specialized ethical reflection. This lack of engagement risks leaving social robotics to evolve without ethical oversight, or to develop normative frameworks in isolation from critical ethical expertise. As a consequence, social robotics may evolve along trajectories shaped more by short-term priorities, market demands or implicit design assumptions than by critical reflection or long-term societal vision—potentially compromising the goal of sustainable and socially responsive integration.

To address these limitations, we propose *synthetic ethics* as an alternative ethical framework which transcends the strong/weak dichotomy and the simplistic rejection of mixed human–robot social ecologies. Synthetic ethics is explicitly grounded in the synthetic method, namely, an approach to scientific inquiry, based on “understanding by building” (Pfeifer & Scheier, 2001), which is typical of the sciences of the artificial (social robotics included) and produces knowledge through iterative cycles of construction and evaluation. As such, synthetic ethics treats ethical uncertainty not as a limitation but as an opportunity: it transforms individuated risks into research questions, which it uses to guide the development of concrete, situated solutions. These questions may include:

- How do different forms of human–robot interaction affect users’ sense of social connection or isolation?

- In what ways might robots reshape the norms and expectations of social behavior in specific contexts (e.g., caregiving, education, public spaces)?
- What kinds of dependencies might be generated by the presence of social robots, and under what conditions are these dependencies ethically acceptable or problematic?
- How do individuals negotiate trust, vulnerability, or intimacy with robotic social agents in co-regulated interactions?
- What institutional or cultural frameworks are needed to ensure that human–robot relations promote, rather than undermine, social inclusion and equity?

In the context of synthetic ethics, these are not hypothetical concerns, to be addressed in the abstract, but concrete questions that emerge through the synthetic process of building and testing social robots in context.

For instance, a synthetic ethics approach could inform the iterative development of companion robots in eldercare by assessing how different interaction modalities affect residents' emotional well-being, social engagement, and autonomy over time. Imagine a scenario where a robot facilitates a daily storytelling session, helping a resident with early-stage dementia recall biographical episodes through co-regulated interaction. The focus of the ethical inquiry here would not target the robot's capacity to "understand," but its ability to sustain affective continuity and reinforce the person's social engagement through shared rhythms and responsive presence. Such applications underscore that the ethical stakes are not located in the robot's internal architecture, but in the social fabric the robot helps co-create. Similarly, educational robots deployed in inclusive classrooms might be studied not for their ability to simulate emotions, but for how they shape peer dynamics, foster collaborative learning, or unintentionally reinforce bias. Consider a situation in which a robot facilitates turn-taking in group activities among neurodiverse children by recognizing and modulating group tensions. While the robot does not "feel," its embedded role in the classroom may support forms of inclusion and participation otherwise difficult to maintain, thus raising nuanced questions of educational fairness and relational agency. Further applications could include robots in public transport hubs, tasked with guiding passengers and modulating crowd dynamics. Here, synthetic ethics would focus not on the robot's ability to simulate empathy, but on how its presence influences collective behavior, facilitates navigation, and affects inclusivity in high-pressure social environments.

In the practice of synthetic ethics, these experimental cases not only inform ethical judgments, but also provide feedback loops to improve design and integration processes. On these bases, synthetic ethics defines itself not merely as a normative stance, but as a methodological framework that uses the design, implementation, and testing of social robots as an experimental field for critically exploring the ethical dimensions of human–robot interaction.

Synthetic ethics is informed by the Aristotelian notion of prudence or *phronesis*: a kind of practical wisdom that is not the application of universal rules, but a context-sensitive discernment that emerges through experience, deliberation and cautious openness to novelty in concrete situations—*akin to navigating a stormy sea*. In Aristotle's ethics, *phronesis* is not the application of universal rules, but a context-sensitive practical wisdom that emerges through experience, deliberation, and a cautious openness to novelty in concrete situations. It is precisely this openness—the

capacity to attend to the unforeseen and the unprecedented—that makes *phronesis* particularly relevant for navigating the ethical challenges posed by rapidly evolving social technologies. Synthetic ethics thus rejects top-down ethical prescriptions in favor of situated ethical judgment developed through the iterative, interactive practice of building and evaluating artificial agents within real social contexts. It is neither inherently negative nor uncritically positive; rather, it is a critical and generative approach, precisely because it is grounded in experimental practice and open to the epistemic and normative uncertainties introduced by emerging social technologies.

While this approach shares affinities with critical design ethics (Dunne & Raby, 2013) and value-sensitive design (Friedman & Hendry, 2019), it departs from both by embracing ethical indeterminacy not as a flaw to be managed, but as a generative condition of the design process itself. Unlike value-sensitive design, which typically starts from eliciting stakeholder values, synthetic ethics treats value formation itself as emerging through interactive design processes. And while critical design ethics emphasizes speculative provocation, synthetic ethics is operational: it unfolds through real-world building, testing, and iteration. Its core contribution lies in embracing ethical indeterminacy as a productive condition for inquiry and innovation.

Central to synthetic ethics is the recognition, based on our relational conception of social competence, that meaningful sociality arises from interactive and emergent properties of human–robot coordination, in such a way that ethical features emerge dynamically from interaction rather than being predetermined by intrinsic attributes of robotic agents. On these grounds, practically, synthetic ethics promotes context-sensitive, case-by-case ethical evaluations, critically examining the concrete implications arising from human–robot interactions. It aims to develop adaptive ethical guidelines attuned to the unique challenges and potentials posed by specific social contexts and interaction scenarios. By actively engaging in all stages of robotic development—from ideation and design to testing and implementation—synthetic ethics seeks not only to integrate ethical reflection within the very fabric of social robotics, but also to systematically explore how human ethical behaviors and value choices evolve through interaction with these novel social machines.

Furthermore, synthetic ethics emphasizes the importance of critically studying our evolving ethical conducts and value choices as we navigate the uncertainty and unpredictability of integrating social robots into our social worlds. By fostering continuous collaboration among diverse stakeholders and embedding ethical deliberation throughout the developmental process, synthetic ethics ensures that social robots function as meaningful "social connectors" (Damiano & Dumouchel, 2020), enhancing rather than diminishing human relationships, and supporting our self-understanding, social development, and moral growth amidst ongoing socio-technological transformations.

As Morton suggests (2016), genuine ethical engagement with the nonhuman requires letting go of fantasies of clarity, control, and "ontological purity." Instead, it calls for an acceptance of co-evolutionary entanglement, as well as of the inherently relational opacity of the world—an opacity that resists predetermined futures and invites openness to the unforeseen. This perspective resonates with the core tenets of synthetic ethics, which does not attempt to eliminate ethical uncertainty, but rather inhabits it as a space for generative, context-bound inquiry.

In this sense, synthetic ethics does not merely respond to ethical challenges *ex post*, but operates as a forward-looking, generative tool. It invites us to ask how human–robot relations might co-evolve with our moral sensibilities, institutional norms, and cultural imaginaries. As such, it offers a distinctive contribution to current debates in Human–AI and Human–Robot Interaction by providing a critical yet pragmatic framework for navigating uncertainty—not by avoiding it, but by using it as a space of ethical and epistemic innovation.

7 Conclusion

This paper has argued that meaningful human–robot sociality does not depend on replicating human-like internal capacities. Indeed, we advanced a relational perspective, where social properties emerge from dynamic coordination within interaction, and a robot’s social value lies not in what it is, but in how it engages affectively and interactively. As argued, this reconceptualization has major ethical implications. It challenges static criteria of authenticity and calls for synthetic ethics: a context-sensitive, practice-based framework for assessing artificial agents. Rather than relying on internal realism, synthetic ethics addresses the situated, evolving dynamics of human–robot coexistence as a space of ethical and epistemic experimentation.

We suggest that this dual framework—relational and ethical—can guide social robotics across diverse domains, from assistive and educational applications to experimental public settings, fostering socially meaningful integration. This dual contribution not only rethinks evaluation criteria, but also offers a pragmatic framework for socially responsible design and deployment.

In closing, one may wonder whether a relational approach could also contribute to reframing the ethical discourse in AI. Much of this discourse still centers on questions of consciousness and the search for universal rules to ensure safety and accountability. Recasting intelligence as a relational property—rather than an individual trait of humans or machines—could open new directions for designing, regulating, and coexisting with artificial agents. As suggested by emerging relational critiques (e.g., Dumouchel, 2019), such a perspective invites a deeper reconsideration of the assumptions that underlie our interactions with AI and the ethical frameworks we apply to them.

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